

TEACHER PROFESSIONAL SKILLS INCREASE FACTORS

Shodmonova Munira Burkhanovna

munira100@mail.ru

Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi, Associate Professor of the Department of Mother Tongue Education, Doctor of Philosophy in Pedagogical Sciences (PhD)
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10803735>

ANNOTATION

In this state, the most significant technological education, practical and professional preparation of the literate secondary school and the system of higher education are in this state.

In the state, there is also a publication of the organization of educational and vocational training and the improvement of qualifications with auxiliary interactive methods, the presentation of opinions on the solution of scientific-methodical problems, the literature of the driver and the process of the improvement of qualifications.

Key words: technology development, economic globalization, high professional;

Today's in the day updated teaching methodology to the student ready knowledge not but education to get different methods , ways recommendation in action. This and own in turn , the people education in the system activity walking pedagogue personnel preparation and their qualification to increase separately attention to give , all in the fields update continue doing today's per day , of teachers professional preparation level even news input , it development and education new to the process to approach requirement in etmok Current science and technology development and economic globalization process xar one from an expert own of the field scholar to be together , mature , each on the front from time one step forward to walk Demand is enough because of personnel qualification increase , this of stage improved system create in specialists high professional to culture , international level knowledge and skills , creative and social to activity to reach important is a condition .

Recognition of our 1st president " If economic growth , development of our society body if so , spirituality , enlightenment and political mind maturity his soul , mind and is his soul . Society development for only of the economy development enough Not citizens , especially well - off young generation , to him education giver of the teacher spiritual consciousness too high level improved to be need

School of teachers qualification increase in the process deep knowledge take qualification increase institutions material and technical base , professors and teachers activity and teaching technologies directly depends . Qualification increase in the system education of technologies application , not only to the course came of the listener knowledge maybe his scientific , creative and intellectual of his authority development his own positive effect shows . Own in turn , qualification to increase came of the audience scientific and creative thought and worldview development for from professors and teachers high skill Demand does Listener and teachers in the middle connection study in the process one series education technologies through done is increased . In particular , mother language and

literature science of teachers qualification increase process in the example who sees if we are , school education complete done in the increase school mother language and literature of teachers service How important if so , here it is of service good quality and efficient in passing of the specialist qualification increase in the courses mastered new knowledge and experiences too so much important is considered

Qualification increase in the courses mother language and literature in their teachers study activity surface to bring and them lessons right , effective organize reach skill and qualifications to form service doer education of types one is this interactive education is counted .

now from interactive ("inter" - " mutual ") education use more and more popular . It is education subjects - teacher , student and students group in the middle surface coming cooperation , intense arguments , mutual thought exchange based on organize is done in the students free thinking , personal their views without hesitation statement is problematic situations solutions together search , study materials in mastering of students mutually their closeness surface bring , " teacher - student - students group » mutual each other respect to understand and support , sincere in relation to be , spiritual to unity achieve etc with is described .

Above to thoughts relied on without to say possibly interactive education is « teacher - student - students between the group mutually cooperation , consensus and to solidarity based on education shape being , students by study of materials fast and efficient to be assimilated provides .

Interactive education methods mother language and literature teachers disputes , problematic situations point kilish , trainings , roles homes , debates , interviews , presentations (or protection) and another to himself special to the conditions have interactive methods with enough level familiar to be to the goal according to Mother tongue and literature teachers qualifications increase in the courses this of the methods use science teachers by of lessons essence , purpose , principles and directions about thorough knowledge , as well as activity right plan get , certain to events about technological map or projects work exit according to professional skill and to qualifications have to be enable will give .

School mother language and literature of teachers professional activities organizational-methodical in terms of right they can organize for modern training using regularly the work take to go their this about there is needs to satisfy help will give . We take went in research experiment works mother so approach based on organize done therefore teachers in the activity significant changes happen it has been and their there is knowledge in practice active to their applications achieved . Below mother that's it about word is conducted .

Cooperation education pedagogue and of the audience educational activity in the process together development , each other deep understand get to each other relatively heartily to feel closeness , activity stages and that's it in stages achieved the results in collaboration analysis from doing consists of is progressive , developing ideas in itself reflection to continue with separately importance occupation is enough Cooperation education the following purposeful directions is based on ;

- pedagogical to goals according to without educational to cooperation based on relationships organize reach
- to the listener humanity ideas based on individual approach ;
- education in the process professional and spiritual of unity decision to find reach

Cooperation of education main idea study assignments together perform and together education to receive mean holds Such education technology in application listeners study assignments in collaboration right perform with together of the group xar one in the member educational activity surface attention to bring focus it is necessary Most cooperation is important pedagogy education to the giver well , education to the recipient even man will give . Each one own behavior consequence about himself thinking will be

Experiment works during cooperation education the following three stage based on applied ;

Stage 1 — qualification increase courses pedagogues education process organize to do preparation they will see in this participants in advance studied , problematic situations happen can be account received without alternative of methods to use attention equipment is available is prepared .

Stage 2 – education process done increase (i.e group work organize problem group in the presence of solution reach their shoulders work exit and the most acceptable ones select).

Stage 3 – education of the process to go and his the results analysis to reach , to the conclusion come

Qualification increase in the system classified from education use mother language and literature of teachers professional preparation level , interests and abilities determination based on to them state requirements from the standards less didn't happen and that's it with one on time different volume and level materials to give will be directed . Qualification increase courses attraction to be rich personal of listeners the work to the experience possessions , that's it with together some listeners while activities to those who started a lot that it was not such as circumstances according to take went research classified from education use efficient that showed . Qualification in raising creative environment heterogeneous (work experience , qualification different according to) and homogeneous (age , experience one different) teams formation with is created . In this classified education homogeneous teams formation through done is increased . of listeners one different level professional preparation have to be training quality and efficiency to increase service does

Qualification in raising study of training the following education forms using organize to be done important importance occupation will be : lecture , seminar, round conversation , debate , question-answer , debate , advice and training .

Today's in the day higher education institutions and qualification increase in institutions lecture texts to prepare separately attention in caratilmok . Them lecture the text statement to be done with together problem on the surface question and assignments is given Lecture in the text scheme , diagrams besides , knowledge , skill and skills scope display it is necessary Lecture in the text in Uzbekistan independence years publication done textbook , manual and another from the literature besides , foreign literature , innovation , advanced the work experience , Internet materials lighting as well as use for books of the list recommendation to be done to the goal is appropriate .

Mother tongue and literature of teachers qualification increase in the process trainer (or andragogues) . training organize mini- lecture , study -discussion , work games , role-playing game , reflection , as well as educational activity surface bringer of the methods efficient to use separately attention was directed .

Lecture method based on training organize in reaching as follows the work viewed :

teacher en lecture one how many important to departments every 15-20 minutes after short for a period of time to stop does To the topic about current some problems in particular questions giving goes Under study problem on the surface thought notice for to the audience possibility will give . Conversation during all of the audience active participation reach for conditions is created . 3-5 minutes debate organize of listeners activities to the increase trust harvest After that , the lecture continue will be delivered . Such approach in the audience interest surface brings Lecture during of the subject slowly mother language and literature teachers the work activity with connection while of training more efficient the passing of provides .

Mother tongue and literature of teachers qualification in raising used interactive of methods again one is this is a discussion . Discuss importance that is , him organize reach in the process of the audience educational activities increases ; of colleagues advanced the work experiences with get to know each other experience they exchange ; prospect plans they form and in it importance to be given necessary has been aspects informed will be

So kilib , qualification increase in the system of education modern from technologies efficient use of teachers professional knowledge just get rich no , that's it with together their in courses activities even surface brings , education content to master relatively creative approach encourages . Theoretical analysis , main stage experience works in the process listeners activities study , special methodology using experiment their work organize reach of education modern technologies based on mother language and literature teachers qualification increase of the process the following tools using organize to be done Methodical point of view from the point of view right that showed ; textbook , supplement materials , listeners creative works , methodical recommendations , state education standard , mother language and literature teachers qualification to increase to be placed state requirements and others

Mother tongue and literature to their teachers help as some topics according to of lessons technological map or the project make up tasks to be given in teachers specialty according to skill and qualifications to form service does Projecting process as a result of :

- the listener activity increases , to cooperation is called ;
- created program , manual , lecture texts with work skill is formed ;
- independent reading to do skill , qualification is developed ;
- own his opinion tell takes , protection does , proves and practical in action uses

Mother tongue and literature teachers qualification increase in the process above such as of the methods use their theoretical knowledge strengthening , practical skill and qualifications more to develop help will give . These are exercises of lessons efficiency to increase service doer new pedagogical and Methodical knowledge , modern technologies , the person learning methods with harmonious without take requires going . That 's it on purpose organize done training alone without , small and big groups as well as public way take to go recommendation done

Research during courses of activity efficiency literature of teachers qualification to increase putable social requirements according to recommendation done system based on analysis done .

Analysis the following three to the criterion basically :

1. Course of education listeners needs satisfy received

2. Mastered theoretical of knowledge listeners by in practice of its application approximate level

3. Course efficiency given common price

Summary by so to speak , school mother language and literature teachers qualification increase new approach based on organize reach their professional skills increase with together educational of problems prevention get and eliminate in reaching active their participation provides . Theirs qualification increase and professional readiness in development of education modern from technologies use complex , many phased (independent education get —> qualification increase in the courses new pedagogical , methodical knowledge mastery —» proficiency from raising next period) process is this stages between mutually relationship and internal to connect in consideration get to the goal is appropriate . Qualification increase in the courses small lecture , study-discussion , role play game and reflection methods as well as training and Methodical manuals , extra materials , creative works , methodical letters of recommendation , State education standard , literature teacher activity content expressive application such as from tools efficient use education in the process of the audience study activities surface brings Teacher en on if it works , it is available knowledge enriched , professional readiness by developing if it goes and study technique tools , mutual cooperation and systematic basically education process organize If so , yes undoubtedly , in education students up level to knowledge have will be independent and critical thinking skill and qualifications with together the world education standards answer give will receive perfect generation is formed .

References:

1. Karimov I. A. Independence and ideology, Tashkent, 1994, p. 9.
2. Yuldoshev J.G. Theoretical and methodological foundations of professional development (or is it easy to become a teacher? - T.: Teacher. 1998.-208 p.
3. The concept of development of the system of improvement of the qualification of perepodgotovki cadres in the Republic Uzbekistan // Kh.F.Rashidov i drugie.. - T.; Science, 1998.
4. Pedagogical terms dictionary , T.; "Science", 2008
- 5 . « General medium of education theoretical and practical problems ". O' zPFITI . Proceedings of the republican scientific - practical conference . 2009 October 5-6, 228 p.
- 6 . " People education employees qualification increase in the system modern content and methods of improvement scientific and practical foundations ". A. Avloni XTX Q TMOMI Republic in the name of materials of the scientific-practical conference . 2010 May 12-13.
- 7 . " Perfect generation formation spiritual development factor ". O'zMU . scientific and practical conference materials . 2010 April 30, 515 -p.